

THE NOTION OF TRANSLATION TECHNIQUES IN AUDIOVISUAL TRANSLATION

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Annotation: Although we are surviving in the era of technology, interpreters are still facing considerable amount of unsolved questions, challenges and interpretational issues belong to audiovisual translation. Additionally, grammar, punctual and cultural mistakes in subtitling and, dismissing or omitting the main information, to translate the source material in the wrong style in dubbing process are very common in translation. All of the above mentioned problematic conditions in interpretation will be discussed in this article.

Key words: translation, audiovisual translation, modes of audiovisual translation, subtitling, dubbing, translation techniques, translation strategies.

Before investigating translation techniques applied widely in audiovisual translation, overall view about translation techniques should be directed to the center of attention. Along with other textual analysis tools, translation approaches and tactics can be utilized to investigate the operation of translation equivalency. They enable the choices translators make for micro-unit translations of texts to be recognized, categorized, and given names.

A translator must decide which translation technique to utilize, and the viability of that option depends on a number of variables, including the context, the translation's goal, the expectations of the target audience, etc. Accordingly, translation techniques are dynamic and useful by nature, consistent with the dynamism of translation equivalency. The translator chooses which method to use based on a number of factors, including the degree of asymmetry between the two texts and the particulars of the term or expression to be translated in the contexts of the source and the target texts. It should be noted that there are proposals that suggest the terms translation techniques and translation strategies have different roles in problem-solving, with strategies being part of the process and techniques affecting its

outcome. This is despite the fact that the terms are interchangeable in the entry's title, as they are in many definitions and classifications.¹⁸

According to that distinction, a translator's strategy is any method—conscious or unconscious, verbal or nonverbal that they employ to address issues that come up during a translation process that has a clear goal in mind. Translators employ many tactics such as paraphrasing, retranslating, speaking aloud, avoiding terms that are extremely similar to those in the standard text, and searching for information. They also use these strategies for comprehension, such as separating major and secondary concepts, building conceptual linkages, and reformulating. Although strategies open the door to a workable translation unit solution, a specific technique is ultimately what solves the problem.

Certain mechanisms can serve as tactics as well as strategies. For example, paraphrasing can be used to amplify a cultural feature in a target text so that readers can understand it, or it can be used as a reformulation tool to overcome problems in the process. This is not to say that using paraphrase as a method always results in the application of the amplification approach; it can also lead to an adaption, a description, a discursive construction, etc. Whatever the nomenclature, a conceptual distinction between the two mechanisms must be made.¹⁹

The tool for textual study of the operation of translation equivalency is translation procedures. They enable the choices translators make for micro-unit translations of texts to be recognized, categorized, and given names. Translating techniques have an impact on the final product of the translation process; in other words, the approach employed is reflected in the translation's outcome. The selection of a translation technique is based on a discursive process that considers the textual context and aims to target a specific impact or function within the target text. To sum up, translation methods share the following five fundamental traits. They are:

- affect the result of the translation process
- are classified on the basis of comparison with the ST
- are applied to micro-units of text
- are discursive and contextual in nature
- are functional.²⁰

The classification of translation techniques proposed here is a revision of Molina and Hurtado²¹. This proposed classification sets out to: Separate the concept

¹⁸ Komil Jurayev "Tarjima san'ati"; p45.

¹⁹ Fredrick Chaume "Audiovisual translation" p24-26

²⁰ Barkhudarov S. G. "Translation as social action" 1993, p100

of translation techniques from similar notions, including, translation strategies, translation methods and translation errors. Include only procedures corresponding to the translation of texts, omitting those corresponding to the comparison of languages. Preserve the functional nature of translation techniques. The definitions given do not appraise a technique's suitability or correctness, which depends on its situation in the text, context, the translation method chosen, readers' expectations, etc. Maintain the most widely used and accepted terms. Formulate new techniques to explain previously undescribed mechanisms. Terms are sometimes translated by means of two or more techniques in combination. This possibility is included in the proposal of Newmark²², who calls such combinations doubles, triples and quadruples. The classification proposed here features a total of 18 translation techniques. If a translation technique has an opposite technique, that is stated in its definition.

There are a number of proposed translation techniques commonly used audiovisual translation modes.

Adaptation: Making a shift in culture.

Amplification: Adding clarifications (explicatory paraphrasing, footnotes, etc.).

Borrowing: Incorporating a word or expression from another language into a target text.

Calque: Giving a literal translation of a foreign syntagm that expresses a new concept or expression.

Compensation: Including an element of information or a stylistic effect in a different place.

Description: Replacing a term or expression with a description of its form and/or function

Discursive creation: Establishing a temporary equivalence that could never be anticipated out of context.

Established equivalent: Using a term or expression recognized (by a dictionary, through language use) as an equivalent.

Generalization: Using a more general or neutral term.

Linguistic amplification: Adding words without a grammatical or normative need to do so.

²¹ Lucia Molina and Amparo Hurtado Albir "Translation Techniques Revisited: A Dynamic and Functionalist Approach" 2002, p 498

²² Newmark P; "A textbook of translation" 1987; p322

Linguistic compression: Summarizing words without a grammatical or normative need to do so.

Literal translation; Giving a word-for-word translation or expression, but not of a single word.

Particularization: Using a more precise or specific term.

Pragmatic variation: Changing linguistic or paralinguistic elements that affect linguistic variation.

Reduction: Suppressing an element of information.

Substitution (linguistic, paralinguistic): Changing linguistic elements for paralinguistic elements or vice versa.

Transposition: Changing a grammatical category.

References:

1. Barkhudarov S. G. "Translation as social action" 1993, p100
2. Lucia Molina and Amparo Hurtado Albir "Translation Techniques Revisited: A Dynamic and Functionalist Approach" 2002, p 498
3. Komil Jurayev "Tarjima san'ati"; p45.
4. Newmark P; "A textbook of translation" 1987; p322
5. Fredrick Chaume "Audiovisual translation" p24-26

